

Notes

6-Heteropoly Tungstoantimonate(V)

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GIBBS¹ obtained potassium antimonatotungstate, $3K_2O \cdot 2Sb_2O_5 \cdot 6WO_3 \cdot 12.5 H_2O$, by boiling a solution of potassium dihydroantimonate, for a long time with potassium tungstate while Hallopeau² obtained the crystalline compound $2WO_3 \cdot 3KSbO_3 \cdot 8H_2O$, by boiling a solution of potassium paratungstate for several hours with an excess of a solution of antimonous acid. The ratio between the condensing oxides reported by them appears anomalous and their compounds cannot be placed within the norm of heteropoly compounds, rather they can be classified as the double salts. So this investigation attempts to lay down some suitable conditions of formation and preparation of true heteropoly compounds of tungsten, with antimony as the heteroatom.

Experimental

If solutions of any arbitrary concentrations of the reactants are mixed together, they may cause immediate precipitation leading to the formation of a compound with indefinite composition. Hence concentrations of the reactants have been chosen properly. To start with, solutions of M/75 potassium pyroantimonate and M/20 sodium tungstate (acidified with glacial acetic acid) were found to be workable. The variation of pH changes were recorded against the volume when M/20 acidified tungstate solution was gradually added into 30 ml. of M/75 potassium pyroantimonate solution. To corroborate the observations help was taken from the application of thermometric titrimetry³. The results are recorded in figs. 1 and 2. By comparing these two graphs

Fig 1

the range in volume of the reactants could be studied. The end points of the horizontal lines of the graphs were taken into consideration as the limiting amounts to be taken for 30 ml. of M/75 potassium pyroanti-

Fig 2

monate solution. Hence 40 ml. of M/20 sodium tungstate solution (acidified with 7 ml of glacial acetic acid) was refluxed with 30 ml. of M/75 potassium pyroantimonate solution for about an hour. The solution was then evaporated to crystallisation and left overnight when white powdery compound separated which was collected and dried. The complete analysis of the compound was done by chemical and instrumental methods. Tungsten was estimated gravimetrically as WO_3 , by tannin and cinchonine hydrochloride⁴ method, whereas antimony was estimated by reducing $Sb(V)$ to $Sb(III)$ with HCl and KI and thereby titrating the liberated iodine with standard sodium thiosulphate solution⁵. To corroborate these, analytical values of colorimetric estimations of tungsten and antimony were also done by 3-4 dithiol and rhodamine B method⁶. Sodium and potassium were estimated by flame photometric and emission spectroscopic methods. The percentages of water and oxygen were calculated by difference. From the analysis the observed percentage composition of the compound came to Sb, 5.71; W, 52.20; K, 1.82; Na, 6.50 and (water+oxygen), 33.76 against the theoretical values: 5.77, 52.28, 1.85, 6.54 and 33.55 respectively.

For assigning the molecular formula from the above percentage composition data, Keggin's view⁷ for the complex anion $[X^{n+}W_6O_{24}]^{(12-n)-}$ was taken into consideration from atomic ratio of W:O, the percentage of oxygen came to 18.20 and hence the percentage of water will be 15.56. So according to stoichiometric composition, the molecular formula of the compound can be represented as $Na_6K[SbW_6O_{24}] \cdot 18H_2O$ and named as 6-heteropoly tungstoantimonate(V).

Determination of pressure-composition Isothermals: Use was made of the apparatus described by Ray and Sinha⁸ and Bhattacharya and Sinha⁹. Isothermal at 35° in stepwise dissociation process gave rise to two systems with respect to water, which came to 18H₂O/14H₂O and 14H₂O/11H₂O. Isothermal at 45° gave rise to two systems 18H₂O/11H₂O and 11H₂O/8H₂O. This results indicated that between the temperature 35° to 45° only 8H₂O remained as the well bound water molecules, which agreed with the work of Scroggie and Clark¹⁰ with

the comparable compounds. The isothermal have been shown in Fig. 3.

X-ray powder diffraction:—The data on powder diffraction has been considered to be very much useful for the elucidation of structure and phases of heteropoly compounds. But the reports on standard powder files on heteropoly acids are very few¹¹. The relevant data as obtained for 6-tungstoantimonate(V) from a powder photograph have been entered in the form of a standard powder card in Table 1.

Fig 3

TABLE 1

d	3.75	8.7	8.0	8.7	Na ₃ K [SbW ₆ O ₂₄] 18 H ₂ O heteropoly tungstoantimonate					
I/I-	100	40	30	40	d A	I/I-	hKL	d A	I/I-	hKL
					1	2	3	1	2	3
Ra CuKλ	λ=1.5405				8.72	40		2.74		3
Filter	Ni				8.20	22		2.70		16
I/I- Visual strip measurement					8.00	30		8.63		25
Ref. Nil					7.70	20		2.56		24
System: Orthorhombic					6.90	12		2.50		20
a=24.82±0.02					6.40	3		2.38		15
b=10.20±0.02					6.00	3		2.34		11
c=11.10±0.02					5.45	21		2.27		25
Ref. Nil					5.30	3		2.21		13
					5.05	12		2.13		9
					4.90	24		2.10		3
					4.57	20		2.03		3
					4.10	12		1.98		31
					4.00	13		1.95		3
					3.82	22		1.92		21
					3.75	100		1.89		12
					3.65	27		1.870		22
					3.40	37		1.825		3
					3.29	15		1.800		22
					3.22	12		1.72		12
					3.10	12		1.679		9
					3.00	12		1.635		3
					2.97	3		1.602		3
					2.90	12		1.585		3
					2.82	13		1.549		15
					2.77	12				

Analysing the above powder file, the system was found to be orthorhombic with $a=24.82 \pm 0.02$, $b=10.20 \pm 0.02$, $c=11.10 \pm 0.02 \text{ \AA}$ and $\alpha+\beta=\gamma=90^\circ$. So the volume V per unit cell was calculated to be $2.805.68 \text{ \AA}^3$. The space group was uniquely established to be I_4 / a and number of molecules per unit

cell Z was found to be 2. The measured density $\rho_{\text{obs.}}=2.46 \text{ gml}^{-1}$. From the relation $\rho_{\text{obs.}} = \frac{1.66M.Z}{V}$, the molecular weight 'M' of the com-

pound to be 2080 against the theoretical value 2109.8.

Discussion

Application of pH and thermometric studies remove much of the uncertainty about the real amount of reactants to be taken for the preparation of heteropoly compounds. It has been observed that the continuation of addition of the reactants did not indicate any possibility of appearance of higher homologue of the series. The generally accepted principle that the condensation of heteropoly acids and their compounds depend on hydrogen ion concentrations has been further corroborated as the complex anion of the tungstoantimonate appeared within pH 5.50. The structure of the compound can be compared with the structure of complex heteroan-

nion $[X_n W_6 O_{24}]^{12-n-}$ suggested by Keggin⁷, and Illingworth¹². Six WO_6 octahedra are to be arranged in a hexagonal annulus so as to share two corners with each of the two neighbouring octahedra. The central cavity of resulting $[W_6 O_{24}]^{12-}$ will just accommodate one octahedron of SbO_6 . The capacity of Sb to behave with 6-coordination number may have a confirmation from the radius ratio rule, $r_{sb} : r_{O^{2-}}$ as 0.44, predicting a coordination number 6. so for Sb. Large number of water molecules find position in the empty space of the crystal to give a resultant hydrated structure.

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Chalcones. XXIII. Germicides Derived from Acetyl Phenanthrenes and Naphthalene

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CONTINUING our study of potential germicides¹⁻⁷ of biochemical importance, we undertook the preparation, characterization and biochemical screening, against gram (+ve) and (-ve) bacteria, of phenanthryl and naphthyl chalcones. These compounds are of interest not only because they contain an α, β -unsaturated carbonyl linkage as a bridge between a phenanthryl moiety and phenyl nucleus, but also because of the reported multiprotecting biochemical activities viz. antibacterial⁸, antifungal⁹, sedative¹⁰, germicidal¹¹, antifertility¹², etc.

The synthesis of these compounds started by condensation of 2- and 3-acetyl phenanthrenes, 2-hydroxy-1-acetonaphthone with substituted benzaldehydes according to the specified procedure³ (Table 1).

The structure of compounds under study follow from the method of synthesis and are confirmed by their elemental analyses, halochromic effect with Conc. H_2SO_4 , 2:4-DNP preparation and by recording absorption spectra of compounds 1, 3, 10 and 13 in the infrared region. The infrared spectra of compounds contain characteristic frequencies corresponding to the individual peculiar features of their structures, and are investigated mainly for their carbonyl frequency. Thus, the absorption bands in the region 1667-1681 cm^{-1} were characteristic¹³ of α, β -unsaturated ketonic group. The effect of neighbouring groups and bi- and tricyclic rings in the frequency has been discussed in an earlier communication¹². All compounds analysed satisfactorily for C, H and N.

Experimental

2- and 3-acetyl phenanthrenes and 2-hydroxy-1-acetonaphthone were prepared according to the standard procedure.

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